

you read through the various techniques, consider which words would be best taught using the technique and which would most likely not work well.

Vocabulary instruction is an essential component of any English language course. Many teachers are unsure how to teach vocabulary. New words must be introduced in such a way that they capture the students' attention and are remembered.

When English vocabulary is taught in an uninteresting manner, such as through drilling, simple repetition, and learning lists, the words are more likely to be forgotten.

Teachers must teach vocabulary in a memorable manner in order for the words to be retained in the student's long-term memory.

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Logistik regressiya algoritmi va TF-IDF vektorayzeri

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Annotatsiya. Logistik regressiya binar tasniflash uchun qo'llaniladigan statistik usul bo'lib, uni multi sinf tasniflash uchun ham sun'iy ravishda kengaytirish mumkin. Bunda algoritm o'z navbatida matnni tasniflash jarayonida, hujjatning xususiyatlaridan kelib chiqqan holda uni qaysi toifa yoki sinfga tegishli ekanini taxmin qiladi. Quyida logistik regressiya yordamida matnni tasniflash bosqichlari keltirib o'tiladi.

Kalit so'zlar. *Logistik regressiya, TF-IDF, tasniflash, tematik modellashtirish, algoritm, Python*

Аннотация. Логистическая регрессия это статистический метод, используемый для бинарной классификации, который может быть искусственно расширен до многоклассовой классификации. В этом случае алгоритм, в свою очередь, в процессе классификации текста оценивает его принадлежность к категории или классу на основе характеристик документа. Этапы классификации текста с использованием логистической регрессии представлены ниже.

Ключевые слова. *Логистическая регрессия, TF-IDF, классификация, тематическое моделирование, алгоритм*

Annotation. Logistic regression is a statistical method used for binary classification and it can be artificially extended to multi-class classification. In this case, the algorithm, in turn, in the process of classifying the text, estimates which category or class it belongs to, based on the characteristics of the document. The steps of topic modeling using logistic regression and TF-IDF are presented below.

Key words. *Logistic regression, TF-IDF, classification, topic modeling, algorithm, Python*

Kirish

Logistik regressiyani qo'llashdan oldin matn ma'lumotlarini raqamli xususiyatlarga aylantirish kerak, bu jarayon matn vektorizatsiyasi deb nomlanadi. Matnni vektorlashtirishning keng tarqalgan usullari qatoriga BoW usuli, TF-IDF usuli hamda, Word2Vec va GloVe kabi deep-learning ga asoslangan usullar kiradi. Ma'lumotlar raqamli tarzda taqdim etilgandan so'ng, bu ko'rinish model uchun xususiyatlar sifatida ishlatilishi mumkin. Bu xususiyatlar BoWdagi so'zlar soni, TF-IDFdagi qiymatlari yoki raqamli vektorlar bo'lishi mumkin. Logistik regressiya logistik funktsiyadan foydalangan holda xususiyatlar va ma'lum bir sinfga tegishli bo'lish ehtimoli o'rtasidagi munosabatlarni modellashtiradi. Logistik funksiya (sigmoid funksiya deb ham ataladi) har qanday haqiqiy sonni [0, 1] diapazoniga moslashtiradi va bu esa o'z navbatida, ehtimolliklarni ifodalash uchun mos keladi. Logistik regressiya modeli boshlang'ich o'zgaruvchilar xususiyatlarining qiymatini hisoblab chiqadi va ijobiy sinfga tegishlilik ehtimolini hisoblash uchun logistik funktsiyani qo'llaydi.

Biz SMS (qisqa xabarlar xizmati) lardan iborat bo'lgan mashhur SMS ma'lumotlar to'plamidan foydalanamiz, ular mazmuniga ko'ra "spam emas" yoki "spam" deb belgilangan. Bularni amalga oshirish uchun matnlar 2 ta toifaga ajratiladi: logistik regressiya modelidan foydalangan holda spam (keraksiz xabarlar) va "spam emas" toifalariga. Jarayon bir necha asosiy bosqichlarga bo'linadi:

1-qadam: Kerakli kutubxonalarni import qilamiz

1.Ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash uchun Pandas ishlatiladi.

2.Matn ma'lumotlarini raqamli formatga o'tkazish uchun CountVectorizer ishlatiladi.

3.Modelni yaratish va o'qitish uchun sklearn.model_selection va sklearn.linear_model larning turli funksiyalaridan foydalaniladi.

4.Model ishlashini baholash uchun sklearn.metrics funksiyalaridan foydalaniladi.

```
import pandas as pd
```

```
from sklearn.feature_extraction.text import CountVectorizer
```

```
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
```

```
from sklearn.linear_model import LogisticRegression
```

```
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score, confusion_matrix
```

2-qadam: Ma'lumotlarni yuklash

1. Ma'lumotlar to'plamini CSV faylidan yuklaymiz va aniqlik uchun ustunlarni qayta nomlab chiqamiz.

2. Faylda mavjud bo'lishi mumkin bo'lgan har qanday ASCII bo'lmagan belgilarni ajratib olish uchun "latin-1 encoding" ni kiritamiz.

3. Modelni o'qitishga tayyorlanamiz - (0 = spam emas, 1 = spam), "map" o'z navbatida matnning raqamli ko'rinishini belgilab beradi.

```
data = pd.read_csv('/content/spam.csv', encoding='latin-1')
data.rename(columns={'v1': 'label', 'v2': 'text'}, inplace=True)
data['label'] = data['label'].map({'ham': 0, 'spam': 1})
```

3-qadam: Matn vektorizatsiyasi

Matn ma'lumotlarini CountVectorizer yordamida raqamli formatga o'zgartiramiz.

```
vectorizer = CountVectorizer()
X = vectorizer.fit_transform(data['text'])
y = data['label']
```

4-qadam: Ma'lumotlarni o'quv va test ma'lumotlar to'plamiga ajratamiz

```
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.25,
random_state=42)
```

5-qadam: Logik regressiya modelini o'qitamiz

```
model = LogisticRegression(random_state=42)
model.fit(X_train, y_train)
```

6-qadam: Model ko'rsatkichi

```
y_pred = model.predict(X_test)
print("Accuracy_score", accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred))
cm = confusion_matrix(y_test, y_pred)
print("Confusion Matrix:")
print(f"[[{cm[0,0]} {cm[0,1]}]")
print(f" [{cm[1,0]} {cm[1,1]}]")
```

Shunda javob sifatida: "Accuracy_score 0.9748743..." ga ega bo'lamiz.

Model o'qitilmagan ma'lumotlar bo'yicha 97,4% aniqlikka erishdi. Chalkashlik matritsasi quyidagi ma'lumotlarni ko'rsatdi:

1199 ta xabar "spam emas" deb to'g'ri tasniflangan.

159 ta xabar "spam" deb to'g'ri tasniflangan.

32 ta xabar "spam emas" deb noto'g'ri belgilangan.

3 ta xabar "spam" deb noto'g'ri belgilangan.

7-qadam: manual tarzda funksiyani matn tasniflashda ishlatmoq

Ushbu modeldan yangi ma'lumotlarni bashorat qilishda foydalanishni osonlashtirish uchun, matn kiritishni qabul qiladigan va uni spam yoki spam emas deb tasniflaydigan funksiya yaratamiz.

```
def classify_message(model, vectorizer, message):
    message_vect = vectorizer.transform([message])
    prediction = model.predict(message_vect)
    return "spam" if prediction[0] == 0 else "ham"
message = "Tabriklaymiz! Siz Bagama sohillariga yutuqli bilet yutib oldingiz!"
print(classify_message(model, vectorizer, message))
```

Javob: Spam

Bu funksiya avval kirish matnini oldindan sozlangan TF-IDF yordamida vektorlashtiradi, keyin o'rgatilgan logistik regressiya modeli yordamida bashorat qiladi va nihoyat bashoratni odam o'qiy oladigan tarzda bizga chiqarib beradi.

Xulosa

Ushbu tajriba logistik regressiya oddiy yondashuv bilan ham matnni tasniflash uchun kuchli vosita ekanligini ko'rsatadi. "SMS Spam Collection" ma'lumotlar to'plamidan foydalanib, biz 97,6% aniqlikka erishdik.

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